

Three questions to EGM

Interview with Romain Magnani, BioReCer Work Package 5 leader

Please explain the BIT, the BioReCer Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-Tool, in three sentences!

The BIT is the technical platform which allows all actors to make educated decisions for enhancing environmental performance, traceability, and improve social acceptance of bioproducts. Thanks to digital components such as web applications for supply chain exploration, interfaces for data monitoring, maps for products traceability and visualisation, and customisable Decision Support System to ease decision-making, the BIT provides the tools to empower stakeholders to reach the project goals with real-time access to context-rich information.

What specific features distinguishes the BIT from generic resource management software?

The BIT uses in the background the European NGS-LD standard which is designed for interoperability, scalability, and openness, allowing stakeholders to effectively manage and leverage their data. It allows for powerful features of Context Information Management such as geographical contextualisation of data, combined with temporal contextualisation. Therefore, it enables complex scenarios involving multiple data stream from sensors, forms, and other information systems in general. Thanks to this approach, the BIT gives the framework to explore the supply chain of a product, understand the temporal and/or geographical context of its generation or its usage in the transformation of another product.

In what ways does your ICT-tool enable stakeholders to access and interpret sustainability indicators, and how do you ensure that this information is presented in a user-friendly and actionable format?

To access and interpret sustainability indicators, the BIT provides specifically designed user interfaces. For example, we designed a screen where a product can be inspected to see details about its life cycle: what products came as inputs for its generation, and what products are generated from it. What transformation process was used, where is its last known storage location, where and how it travelled. Each step has its own calculations in terms of energy requirements and consumptions. These types of screens are co-designed with the help of the stakeholders to make sure they respond accordingly to their needs, in respect of state-of-the-art usability guidelines.